

Type of the Paper (Article, Review, Communication, etc.)

Performance Evaluation of Low-Cost Formaldehyde Sensors under Controlled and Dynamic Environmental Conditions

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What are the main findings?

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- Second bullet.

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- First bullet.
- Second bullet.

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1. Introduction

Indoor air quality (IAQ) has become a key determinant of public health and well-being, as people spend approximately 90% of their time indoors, including in homes, workplaces, and transportation environments. Prolonged exposure to pollutants has been associated with respiratory disease, cardiovascular morbidity, cancer, and cognitive impairment. According to the World Health Organization, in 2021 household air pollution was responsible for an estimated 2.9 million premature deaths annually, highlighting the need to address this issue from a scientific perspective focused on prevention and continuous control.

In this context, understanding the nature and behavior of pollutants present in indoor environments is essential. These include a wide range of chemical, physical, and biological substances, such as particulate matter, carbon dioxide (CO₂), spores, bacteria, allergens, and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). Although international organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO) have established guideline values for several indoor pollutants, regulatory frameworks for indoor air quality remain less developed and, in many cases, non-binding compared to outdoor air quality legislation. In numerous European countries, specific legal limits for residential environments are lacking, reinforcing the need for reliable monitoring tools to assess and manage exposure.

Among VOCs, formaldehyde stands out as one of the most relevant indoor pollutants due to both its multiple emission sources and its adverse health effects. It can be emitted from combustion processes (e.g., smoking, cooking, incense and candle use), building materials, furniture, and cleaning products, among others. In the European Union, it is classified as a Category 1B carcinogen and a Category 2 mutagen, and exposure has been associated with eye and respiratory irritation, asthma exacerbation, contact dermatitis, and potential neurotoxic, hematological, and reproductive effects.

This combination of multiple emission sources and adverse health impacts makes formaldehyde a priority pollutant in indoor air quality control strategies. Consequently, controlling indoor formaldehyde levels has become a priority in residential and occupational environments. In this regard, the World Health Organization has established a guideline value of 100 µg·m⁻³ as a 30-minute average (approximately 80 ppb) to prevent irritative effects and minimize carcinogenic risks.

Traditionally, the determination of formaldehyde in indoor environments has relied on reference analytical methods, such as sampling using DNPH cartridges followed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis, or gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC/MS). These methods provide high sensitivity and reliability and are widely accepted as reference techniques for carbonyl compound quantification. However, they require specialized instrumentation, trained personnel, and off-site laboratory analysis, making them costly and labor-intensive for long-term monitoring campaigns or large-scale deployments. Furthermore, they typically provide integrated concentrations over the sampling period, limiting their ability to capture rapid fluctuations or short-term emission events. For these reasons, low-cost sensors have emerged as an affordable, easy-to-install, and energy-efficient alternative for real-time indoor monitoring.

In response to these limitations, the development of low-cost formaldehyde sensors has led to various technologies based on different detection principles, including electrochemical sensors, metal oxide (MOX/MOS) sensors, photoacoustic sensors, and colorimetric sensors, which are widely used in indoor air quality monitoring applications. These technologies enable near real-time detection of formaldehyde using compact systems, making them particularly attractive for integration into continuous monitoring devices.

Recent laboratory studies with commercial electrochemical modules such as the Sensirion SFA30 and the DFRobot Gravity have shown that low-cost formaldehyde

sensors can exhibit good linearity ($R^2 > 0.95$), low limits of detection on the order of 10 ppb, and acceptable repeatability over typical indoor concentration ranges. However, these results are generally obtained under controlled experimental conditions and single-compound exposures, which are not fully representative of more realistic environments, where sensor performance may be influenced by additional factors such as cross-sensitivities to other volatile organic compounds, particularly alcohols and other aldehydes. Controlled cross-sensitivity experiments, in which SFA30 and Gravity electrochemical sensors were exposed to mixtures of formaldehyde and gases commonly found in indoor and outdoor environments, have demonstrated that the measured signal can be significantly biased under realistic mixtures, with some interferents producing responses comparable to or even higher than those of formaldehyde at similar ppb levels.

Environmental conditions, particularly temperature and relative humidity, also exert a strong influence on sensor response. In the case of low-cost electrochemical formaldehyde sensors, systematic chamber experiments have shown that, after formaldehyde concentration, temperature is typically the second most influential factor governing the output signal, followed by relative humidity. Similar sensitivities to temperature and humidity have been reported for other sensor types, including MOX and optical or colorimetric systems, in which changes in water content and diffusion properties may affect both baseline levels and sensitivity.

Nevertheless, increases in signal observed under higher temperature conditions cannot be attributed solely to instrumental effects. It has been demonstrated that rising temperatures promote the release of formaldehyde from building materials, leading to higher indoor air concentrations. Therefore, variations recorded by the sensor may reflect both real changes in emission and dependencies associated with the device itself.

As a consequence, the reliability of measurements in real indoor environments may be compromised, particularly when mixtures of VOCs, variable occupancy patterns, and fluctuations in temperature and humidity coexist. For this reason, several authors emphasize the importance of evaluating and validating sensor performance under controlled laboratory conditions using reference methods prior to large-scale deployment. Furthermore, studies focused on the selection and evaluation of commercial low-cost devices for indoor air quality monitoring, such as in school environments, highlight that pre-deployment testing, co-location with reference instruments, and periodic quality control procedures are essential to ensure that continuous monitoring based on low-cost formaldehyde sensors provides data of sufficient quality for health-related assessments and building management purposes.

Although previous studies have addressed specific aspects of commercial sensor performance, there remains a need for comprehensive evaluations that combine validation against reference methods with systematic analysis of cross-sensitivities and environmental parameter influences within a unified experimental framework.

In this context, the present work aims to systematically evaluate the performance of low-cost formaldehyde sensors under different environmental conditions by combining controlled laboratory experiments with tests conducted under more realistic indoor scenarios, and by comparing the results with those obtained using the HPLC/DNPH reference method. Sensor responses to different formaldehyde concentrations under controlled ranges of temperature and relative humidity are analyzed, as well as their behavior under more dynamic and representative conditions, in order to identify potential deviations, environmental dependencies, and operational limitations. The results provide experimental evidence regarding the reliability of these devices for continuous indoor air quality monitoring and contribute to defining the conditions under which their use may be appropriate.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study design

This study was designed to evaluate the performance of a low-cost electrochemical formaldehyde sensor under progressively complex experimental conditions. Rather than conducting a full metrological validation, the study focused on evaluating whether the sensor provides sufficiently reliable information for continuous indoor monitoring and decision-support purposes, while also identifying conditions that may compromise its performance.

The experimental approach was structured in four complementary stages: controlled chamber verification against a reference analytical method, qualitative cross-sensitivity assessment, evaluation of sensor degradation after exposure to elevated formaldehyde concentrations, and deployment in real indoor environments.

Controlled chamber experiments were carried out in a 1 m³ chamber to assess sensor response to formaldehyde under defined environmental conditions. Reference measurements were performed using DNPH cartridge sampling followed by HPLC analysis in order to independently determine formaldehyde concentrations and evaluate the agreement between sensor readings and analytically derived values. These verification experiments included different temperature and relative humidity conditions, allowing the influence of environmental variability on sensor performance to be assessed within the reference-comparison framework. Furthermore, measurements obtained from sensors with different operational histories were compared. Some monitoring units incorporated recently replaced formaldehyde sensors, whereas others retained sensors that had been operating for longer periods and had previously been exposed to environments with elevated formaldehyde concentrations.

Additional chamber experiments were conducted to qualitatively evaluate cross-sensitivities to selected volatile and inorganic compounds.

Finally, the sensor was deployed in indoor environments, including a semi-controlled meeting room and occupied residential dwellings, to assess its behaviour under representative operating conditions.

2.2 Sensor Device and Monitoring System

Measurements were performed using the commercial indoor air quality monitoring device InBiot MICA, which integrates multiple environmental sensors for continuous indoor monitoring.

Formaldehyde measurements were based on the Sensirion SFA30 electrochemical module, specifically designed for ppb-level indoor air quality applications. According to the manufacturer specifications¹, the sensor has a measurement range of 0–1000 ppb with a resolution of 1 ppb. Under reference conditions (25 °C and 50% relative humidity), the stated accuracy is ±20 ppb or ±20% of the measured value (whichever is greater) within the 0–200 ppb range, and the repeatability is ±5 ppb or ±5%.

In addition to formaldehyde, the device records temperature, relative humidity, carbon dioxide (CO₂), total volatile organic compounds (TVOC), and particulate matter concentrations. These auxiliary parameters were used to characterize environmental conditions during the experiments.

Sensor data were recorded at fixed intervals of 10 minutes and stored digitally for subsequent analysis. The devices were operated continuously throughout the experimental campaigns, without applying additional external corrections beyond the internal processing implemented by the manufacturer.

¹ https://sensirion.com/media/documents/DEB1C6D6/6789009D/GAS_DS_SFA30_D1.pdf

2.3 Controlled Chamber Experiments

2.3.1 Chamber Setup

Controlled experiments were conducted in a custom-built 1 m³ methacrylate chamber designed to generate defined indoor-like atmospheres.

The chamber was equipped with an internal fan to ensure air homogenization, an injection port with septum for compound introduction, and an outlet port for air sampling. The monitoring devices were placed inside the chamber and operated continuously during the experiments.

Before each experiment, the chamber was ventilated until background conditions returned close to initial levels in order to minimize residual effects from previous tests.

2.3.2 Formaldehyde Generation and Experimental Duration

Formaldehyde atmospheres were generated by injecting varying volumes of a methanol-stabilized formaldehyde solution through the septum port while the chamber remained sealed. The injected volume was adjusted according to the target concentration required for each experiment.

Following injection, the internal fan ensured air mixing until a stable concentration plateau was reached. The evolution of the sensor signal was monitored continuously during this stabilization period. Each experiment lasted approximately one day, including the stabilization phase after injection and the subsequent DNPH sampling procedures.

Once steady-state conditions were achieved, air samples were collected for reference analysis as described in Section 2.4.

2.3.3 Environmental Condition Experiments

Environmental condition experiments were conducted after stable formaldehyde concentrations had been established in the chamber. Four different scenarios were evaluated: (i) baseline conditions with temperature and relative humidity at normal indoor levels, (ii) increased temperature at approximately constant relative humidity, (iii) increased relative humidity at approximately constant temperature, and (iv) simultaneous increments of temperature and relative humidity.

The environmental conditions evaluated in the chamber experiments are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

Experiment	Experimental conditions	Temperature (°C)	Relative Humidity (%RH)
Experiment 1	High formaldehyde concentration (Normal indoor conditions)	24.2	48.0
Experiment 2	High formaldehyde concentration (Normal indoor conditions)	23.6	48.6
Experiment 3	High-humidity conditions	20.3	83.3
Experiment 4	High-humidity conditions	20.8	82.3
Experiment 5	Normal indoor concentration	21.5	50.6
Experiment 6	High-temperature conditions	29.0	40.4
Experiment 7	Normal indoor conditions	21.8	42.1
Experiment 8	Normal indoor conditions	22.3	44.2

Temperature increments were achieved by introducing a heat source inside the chamber, allowing progressive increases in air temperature while continuously

monitoring the sensor response. Relative humidity increments were achieved by introducing a controlled water vapor source inside the chamber while maintaining temperature approximately constant.

These experiments were designed to assess sensor behaviour under modified environmental conditions and to distinguish between concentration changes caused by physicochemical processes within the chamber (e.g., thermal desorption from surfaces) and potential environmental sensitivity of the electrochemical sensing principle itself.

By performing environmental increments without introducing additional formaldehyde, it was possible to evaluate whether observed concentration increases were associated with real changes in chamber air composition or with direct sensor response to temperature and humidity variations.

2.3.4 Cross-Sensitivity Assessment

Qualitative cross-sensitivity tests were conducted to evaluate the potential influence of selected volatile compounds on the formaldehyde sensor signal.

Prior to each experiment, the chamber was ventilated to reduce formaldehyde concentrations to minimal background levels. The chamber atmosphere was then allowed to stabilize for 30 minutes. Once stabilized, different compounds were injected into the chamber without adding additional formaldehyde, and the sensor response was continuously recorded. The list of compounds evaluated in the chamber is presented in Table X.

Methanol
Acetone
Ethanol
Formic Acid
Acetaldehyde
2-Propanol
Acetic Acid
Toluene
NO ₂
O ₃

For VOC experiments (e.g., methanol, ethanol, acetaldehyde, toluene, and other organic compounds), the presence of the injected compounds in the chamber was monitored using the integrated TVOC sensor available in the device. This allowed verification of compound introduction and qualitative tracking of their temporal evolution in the chamber atmosphere. For these compounds, 1 µL was injected into the chamber. In the case of acetaldehyde, X µL of headspace were injected due to the difficulty of handling this compound in liquid phase.

For inorganic gases, NO₂ and O₃ concentrations were monitored using the specific gas sensors integrated in some of the devices used in the experiment. These measurements were used to confirm the presence and temporal evolution of these gases during the tests. NO₂ was introduced using a XXXX system, applying a flow of XXX for XXX time. Ozone (O₃) was generated using a XX device and injected at a flow of XXX for XX time.

The objective of these experiments was to evaluate whether the sensor exhibited measurable signals in the presence of volatile compounds other than formaldehyde, in order to identify potential cross-sensitivities. This evaluation was purely qualitative, and no quantitative cross-interference coefficients were determined.

All tests were performed while maintaining constant baseline environmental conditions, except for the introduction of the target compound, allowing assessment of the direct impact of each potential interferent on the sensor signal.

2.4 Real conditions environment

The second environment was a meeting room located at CARTIF's facilities. This location was selected due to the detection of unusually high formaldehyde concentrations caused by the varnishing of a wooden meeting table. Although it can still be considered a controlled space, since the room typically remains closed unless it is in use and efforts were made to keep it closed before and during the tests, the building's mechanical ventilation system introduces a more realistic degree of variability, as some measurements were taken during or shortly after ventilation events. During selected periods, air samples were collected for reference analysis as described in Section 2.4.

Four sampling campaigns were carried out over three different days. The first two samplings were conducted consecutively, while the third and fourth were performed at different times of the day, including early morning and mid-morning conditions. Each sampling lasted approximately one hour, during which both continuous sensor measurements and integrated air samples were collected.

The low-cost sensor device recorded formaldehyde concentrations and additional environmental parameters, including temperature, relative humidity, CO₂, and TVOC index, allowing the characterization of the indoor conditions during each sampling period.

In addition to formaldehyde, acetaldehyde was also considered in the analysis, as it is one of the carbonyl compounds quantified by the DNPH-HPLC method and is known to exhibit cross-sensitivity in electrochemical formaldehyde sensors.

The third study environment consisted of different residential dwellings. The results obtained in this case were purely exploratory, as no comparison with any reference method was performed. The main objective was to analyze the evolution of the different parameters under more realistic conditions and to assess how everyday activities influence indoor air quality, as well as how the sensors respond to these activities.

2.5 Reference method (DNPH-HPLC)

Formaldehyde determination was performed according to UNE 77260 for indoor carbonyl compounds using DNPH cartridge sampling followed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis.

Air sampling was carried out using Gillian 800i pumps at a flow rate of 0.5 L min⁻¹ for 60 minutes, corresponding to a total sampled air volume of 30 L. DNPH cartridges (PK50 3 mL / 350 mg DNPH ReZorian Tube, Merck Life Science) were used for collection. After sampling, the cartridges were eluted with HPLC-grade acetonitrile (99.9%), and the resulting extracts were analyzed by HPLC.

The chromatographic analysis was conducted using an HPLC system (Perkin Elmer, model Flexar, USA) equipped with a binary pump (5200/Flexar Binary Pump/225) and a UV-Vis detector (200 series UV-vis Detector) set at 360 nm. Separation of the formaldehyde–DNPH derivative was achieved using an analytical C18 column (Agilent ZORBAX Eclipse Plus, 150 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 3.5 μm particle size). An isocratic mobile phase consisting of 40% water and 60% acetonitrile was used at a flow rate of 1.00 mL min⁻¹. The total run time was 25 minutes. Samples were manually injected using a syringe with an injection volume of 20 μL. Peak areas were integrated using the instrument software.

Formaldehyde was calibrated simultaneously with a suite of aldehydes and ketones using a commercial standard mixture containing 12 target compounds (Sigma-Aldrich,

Germany). Calibration curves were generated by preparing standards at different concentration levels and manually injecting 20 μL of each standard into the injection system.

The analytical procedure was consistent with previously reported validation approaches for gaseous formaldehyde determination.

3. Results

The performance of the formaldehyde sensors was evaluated through a stepwise experimental approach. First, sensor measurements were compared with concentrations determined by the DNPH-HPLC reference method under different environmental conditions representative of indoor environments. Subsequently, the influence of sensor operational history was assessed by comparing recently replaced sensors with sensors that had been previously exposed to elevated formaldehyde concentrations. Additional experiments were conducted to investigate cross-sensitivities to selected volatile and inorganic compounds. Finally, the applicability of the sensors for indoor air quality monitoring was evaluated under real operating conditions.

3.1. Verification against DNPH

3.1.1 Verification under different environmental conditions

The agreement between the formaldehyde sensor and the DNPH-HPLC reference method was evaluated under a range of conditions representative of indoor environments, including low and elevated formaldehyde concentrations, increased relative humidity, and elevated temperature. The objective was to assess whether variations in pollutant levels and environmental conditions affected the sensor's ability to reproduce the concentrations determined by the reference method.

Three formaldehyde sensors were evaluated during the experimental campaign. The concentrations reported by each sensor are presented in Table X together with the concentrations determined by the DNPH-HPLC reference method. Results are presented both for formaldehyde alone and for the combined concentration of formaldehyde and acetaldehyde.

Experiment	Experimental conditions	Sensor 1 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	Sensor 2 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	Sensor 3 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	HPLC Formaldehyde ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	HPLC Formaldehyde + acetaldehyde ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)
Experiment 1	High formaldehyde concentration (Normal indoor conditions)	150.4	157.0	169.8	162.35	18.58
Experiment 2	High formaldehyde concentration (Normal indoor conditions)	144.2	150.4	161.8	150.34	23.31
Experiment 3	High-humidity conditions	99.6	103.0	110.4	86.97	12.17
Experiment 4	High-humidity conditions	96.4	100.2	107.8	88.81	15.50
Experiment 5	Normal indoor concentration	43.6	47.8	49.8	25.01	8.64
Experiment 6	High-temperature conditions	84.0	90.0	96.5	51.99	24.12
Experiment 7	Normal indoor conditions	2.6	3.2	5.8	4.01	2.93
Experiment 8	Normal indoor conditions	36.2	39.6	45.2	18.68	11.44

As shown in Table X and Figure 5A, the relationship between the sensor response and the reference concentrations depended on the experimental condition. Under elevated formaldehyde concentrations (Experiments 1 and 2), the mean sensor response was close to the formaldehyde concentrations determined by HPLC. In contrast, at lower concentration levels (Experiments 5, 7 and 8), the sensor response showed closer agreement with the combined concentration of formaldehyde and acetaldehyde. A similar trend was observed under high relative humidity conditions (Experiments 3 and 4), where the sensor response was also closer to the total aldehyde concentration than to formaldehyde alone. The high-temperature experiment (Experiment 6) showed the largest deviation from the HPLC formaldehyde concentration. However, the difference decreased considerably when the combined concentration of formaldehyde and acetaldehyde was used as the reference.

To facilitate the interpretation of these differences, the absolute error between the mean sensor response and the reference concentration was normalised using the assumed sensor uncertainty. The results are presented in Figures 5B and 5C for formaldehyde and formaldehyde plus acetaldehyde, respectively. Values below 1 indicate that the difference between the sensor response and the reference concentration remains within the uncertainty interval and can therefore be considered compatible with the reference method.

U = max(25 µg/m³, 20% of the sensor reading). Values below the dashed line are compatible with the reference within sensor uncertainty.

When formaldehyde alone was used as the reference endpoint (Figure 5B), the mean sensor response remained within the uncertainty interval for all experiments except the high-temperature condition (Experiment 6). Under elevated formaldehyde concentrations (Experiments 1 and 2), high relative humidity (Experiments 3 and 4), and low indoor-like

concentrations (Experiments 5, 7 and 8), the normalised error remained below the compatibility threshold.

When the combined concentration of formaldehyde and acetaldehyde was used as the reference endpoint (Figure 5C), all experiments remained within the compatibility threshold, including the high-temperature condition. The lowest normalised errors were observed under high relative humidity conditions (Experiments 3 and 4), whereas larger deviations were observed for the elevated formaldehyde concentration experiments (Experiments 1 and 2), although these remained within the assumed uncertainty limits.

3.1.2 Comparison between sensors with different operational histories

To investigate whether sensor performance was influenced by operational history, measurements obtained from sensors that had been operating for extended periods were compared with those obtained from recently replaced sensors. All experiments described in Section 3.1.1 were included in the analysis, allowing both sensor groups to be evaluated against the same reference concentrations and under identical environmental conditions.

Figure 6 compares the response of both sensor groups with the concentrations determined by the DNPH-HPLC reference method. The recently replaced sensors showed a closer agreement with the reference concentrations than the sensors with a longer operational history for both reference endpoints. When formaldehyde was used as the reference, the mean absolute error (MAE) decreased from 27.87 to 14.64 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. When the combined concentration of formaldehyde and acetaldehyde was used as the reference, the MAE decreased from 31.41 to 11.52 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Similarly, the coefficient of determination increased from 0.71 to 0.95 for formaldehyde and from 0.78 to 0.97 for the combined aldehyde endpoint.

Considering the assumed sensor uncertainty of $\pm 25 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ or $\pm 20\%$ of the sensor reading, whichever was greater, the mean response of the recently replaced sensors remained compatible with the formaldehyde reference in 7 of the 8 experiments and with the total aldehyde reference in all experiments. For the sensors with a longer operational history, compatibility was observed in 5 of 8 and 3 of 8 experiments, respectively.

The improvement was also evaluated on an experiment-by-experiment basis. Figure 7 shows the absolute error of the mean response of each sensor group relative to the reference method for all experimental conditions. The recently replaced sensors exhibited lower absolute errors in 5 of the 8 experiments when formaldehyde was used as the reference endpoint and in 6 of the 8 experiments when the combined concentration of formaldehyde and acetaldehyde was considered. The largest reductions in error were observed under elevated formaldehyde concentrations and high relative humidity conditions.

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The agreement between sensor groups and the reference method was further assessed using Bland–Altman analysis. When formaldehyde alone was used as the reference endpoint, the sensors with a longer operational history showed a mean bias of $-5.0 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, whereas the recently replaced sensors showed a mean bias of $13.8 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Larger differences were observed when the comparison was performed against the combined formaldehyde and acetaldehyde endpoint, with a mean bias of $-19.6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for the sensors with a longer operational history and $-0.8 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for the recently replaced sensors. In addition, the recently replaced sensors exhibited a closer clustering of observations around the mean bias line, indicating improved agreement with the reference method across the range of concentrations evaluated.

3.3 Cross-sensitivity Assessment

Qualitative cross-sensitivity tests were conducted to evaluate the response of the formaldehyde sensor to different volatile compounds. The temporal evolution of the sensor signal after the injection of each compound is presented in Figure X.

For VOC experiments, the figures show the simultaneous response of the TVOC index and the formaldehyde sensor. In all cases, the TVOC signal increased after compound injection, confirming the presence of the injected compound in the chamber. The magnitude and temporal evolution of the TVOC response varied depending on the compound.

The formaldehyde sensor response differed among the tested VOCs. Alcohols, including methanol, ethanol, and isopropanol, produced observable increases in the formaldehyde signal following injection. These responses were characterized by an increase after compound introduction, followed by stabilization over time.

Acetaldehyde also induced a clear response in the formaldehyde sensor, with a temporal evolution comparable to that observed for alcohols, although occurring within a lower concentration range. It should be noted that the chamber atmosphere already contained measurable background concentrations of acetaldehyde, as confirmed by the DNPH-HPLC analyses performed during the validation experiments. Consequently, the apparent increase observed after acetaldehyde injection likely underestimates the overall influence of this compound on the sensor response.

Organic acids showed distinct behaviours. Formic acid produced a strong increase in the formaldehyde signal, while acetic acid also resulted in a noticeable and progressive increase over time. In contrast, toluene showed negligible variation in the formaldehyde signal, despite a clear increase in the TVOC index.

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For inorganic gases, the temporal evolution of formaldehyde and gas concentrations is presented in Figures X and X. In the case of NO_2 , the formaldehyde signal remained initially stable and subsequently decreased as NO_2 concentration increased. For ozone (O_3), the introduction of the gas led to a rapid decrease in the formaldehyde signal, reaching near-zero values while O_3 concentrations increased significantly.

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3.3 Sensor Performance under Real Indoor Conditions

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2.3.1 Comparison with reference measurements

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The comparison between the average formaldehyde concentration measured by the low-cost sensors and the reference values obtained by the DNPH-HPLC method is shown in Figure X.

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2.3.2 Environmental conditions during sampling

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The environmental conditions during the sampling campaigns are shown in Figures X–X, where the temporal evolution of temperature, relative humidity, CO₂ concentration, and TVOC index is presented for each experiment.

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4. Discussion

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Authors should discuss the results and how they can be interpreted from the perspective of previous studies and of the working hypotheses. The findings and their implications should be discussed in the broadest context possible. Future research directions may also be highlighted.

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5. Conclusions

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

MDPI	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute
DOAJ	Directory of open access journals
TLA	Three letter acronym

LD Linear dichroism

Appendix A

Appendix A.1

The appendix is an optional section that can contain details and data supplemental to the main text—for example, explanations of experimental details that would disrupt the flow of the main text but nonetheless remain crucial to understanding and reproducing the research shown; figures of replicates for experiments of which representative data is shown in the main text can be added here if brief, or as Supplementary data. Mathematical proofs of results not central to the paper can be added as an appendix.

Table A1. This is a table caption.

Title 1	Title 2	Title 3
entry 1	data	data
entry 2	data	data

Appendix B

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References

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- Author 1, A.; Author 2, B. Title of the chapter. In *Book Title*, 2nd ed.; Editor 1, A., Editor 2, B., Eds.; Publisher: Publisher Location, Country, 2007; Volume 3, pp. 154–196.
- Author 1, A.; Author 2, B. *Book Title*, 3rd ed.; Publisher: Publisher Location, Country, 2008; pp. 154–196.
- Author 1, A.B.; Author 2, C. Title of Unpublished Work. *Abbreviated Journal Name* year, *phrase indicating stage of publication (submitted; accepted; in press)*.
- Author 1, A.B. (University, City, State, Country); Author 2, C. (Institute, City, State, Country). Personal communication, 2012.
- Author 1, A.B.; Author 2, C.D.; Author 3, E.F. Title of Presentation. In Proceedings of the Name of the Conference, Location of Conference, Country, Date of Conference (Day Month Year).

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574
575